

Microwave assisted synthesis and characterization of some new annulated pyrimidinone derivatives

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Abstract : 4-Aryl-6-methyl-2-pyrimidinone-5-carbohydrazide derivatives have been synthesized from the reaction of different dihydropyrimidinone with hydrazine hydrate. These compounds upon microwave irradiation undergo clean and facile cyclization with chloroacetamide, chloroacetyl chloride and triethylorthoformate and led to the formation of 3-(6-methyl-2-oxo-4-substituted phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-5-yl)-1,6-dihydro-1,2,4-triazin-5(2H)-one, 4-(6-methyl-2-oxo-4-substituted phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-5-yl)tetrahydropyridazine-3,6-dione, 6-methyl-5-(5-oxo-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-4-substitutedphenyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one and their substituted derivatives respectively, in quantitative yield. Structures of these newly synthesized compounds were established on the basis of spectra and analytical data.

Keywords : Microwave irradiation, dihydropyrimidinone, pyridazindione.

3,4-Dihydropyrimidinones derivatives (DHPMs) have received considerable attention with in recent years and emerged as important target molecule due to their attractive therapeutic and pharmacological profiles such as antiviral, antimitotic, anticarcinogenic, antihypertensive agent and noteworthy as a calcium channel blockers, alpha antagonists and neuropeptide (NPY) antagonists¹⁻⁴. The synthesis of this heterocyclic compound and its derivatives is of much current importance⁵⁻⁹. Consequently, the importance of triazinone, pyridazindione, pyrazolinone derivatives and their synthetic analogue is well recognized by synthetic as well as biological chemists¹⁰⁻¹⁸. They have been found to exhibit a broad spectrum of biological activity like antipyretic, diuretic, antiasthmatic, antirheumatic, anticancer, antiviral, antitumour, etc. Therefore, it is worthwhile to incorporate above moieties having diverse and remarkable properties with dihydropyrimidinone nucleus in one molecule to evaluate their effect as anticipated active antimicrobial compounds.

Microwave assisted chemistry has attracted a considerable amount of attention in recent years^{19,20}. Microwave activation as a non conventional energy source has become an important method that can be used to carry out a wide range of reactions with short reaction time, operational simplicity and formation of cleaner products with high yield. Thus growing interest in such methodologies has been opening new horizons in the

search of suitable drug candidates such as heterocyclic systems. Keeping all in view, we report our results related to the synthesis of above heterocyclic systems under microwave irradiation.

Results and discussion

3,4-Dihydropyrimidinones (DHPMs) **1a-c** were obtained by Biginelli reaction employing a three component system comprising ethylacetoacetate with benzaldehyde/substituted benzaldehyde and urea²¹. The carbohydrazide derivatives **2a-c** were prepared via reaction of compound **1a-c** with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol by adding few drops of acetic acid and irradiated under microwave irradiation for 2.5–3 min. These were obtained in 74–80% yield and were characterized fully by spectroscopic and elemental analysis. The IR (KBr) absorption band at 3350, 3280 cm⁻¹ (NH₂ str.) and a singlet of 2H at δ 3.2 in ¹H NMR spectra reveals the presence of NH₂ group. In compounds **1a-c**, C=O str. appears in the range of 1730–1745 cm⁻¹ due to presence of ester group while in compounds **2a-c**, C=O str. appears in the range of 1660–1680 cm⁻¹ due to amide linkage, which confirms the formation of compound **2**.

Triazinone derivatives **3a-c** were synthesized by the reaction of the compound **2** in DMF with chloroacetamide under microwave irradiation for 6–11 min. Structures of the products **3a-c** were established on the basis of spectral

Scheme 1

and analytical data. Formation of triazinone derivatives **3a-c** were evidenced by disappearance of peak of NH_2 group in IR and ^1H NMR spectrum and appearance of signal, a singlet at 3.69 for CH_2 (C-6) of the triazinone ring in ^1H NMR spectrum and the IR (KBr) absorption band at 1621 cm^{-1} due to $\text{C}=\text{N}$ group also confirms the formation of compound **3**.

Reaction of compound **2a-c** in DMF with chloroacetylchloride for about 10–12 min under MWI leads to the formation of pyridazinedione derivatives **4a-c**. The structures of the compounds were deduced by elemental and spectral analysis. IR (KBr) spectrum shows an absorption band at $1680\text{--}1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to cyclic imide group, but confirmation of pyridazindione moiety was done by ^1H NMR spectra, which showed signal at δ

3.31, a triplet for a saturated carbon proton (C-4) and at δ 2.73, a doublet for another saturated carbon proton (C-5).

Syntheses of pyrazolinone derivatives **5a-c** were achieved by the reaction of compound **2a-c** with triethylorthoformate under microwave heating for 5–8 min. The structure of the compound **5a-c** were confirmed mainly by ^1H NMR spectra which shows two characteristic signal, one at δ 8.33, a doublet for olefinic carbon (C-3) and other at δ 4.14, a doublet for C-4 of pyrazolinone moiety and IR spectra shows absorption band at 1611 cm^{-1} , characteristic of $\text{C}=\text{N}$ group. The nature of all the synthesized products is determined by their analytical and spectral data.

Conclusion :

In conclusion, our results demonstrate a simple, mild

Table 1. Characterization data of the synthesized compounds

Compd.	Molecular formula (M.W.)	Irradiation time (min)	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) :		
					Calcd.	(Found)	
					C	H	N
2a	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ (246)	2.5	80	171	58.53 (58.45)	5.69 (5.71)	13.00 (12.99)
2b	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ Cl (280)	3	79	167	51.42 (51.23)	4.64 (4.59)	20.00 (20.01)
2c	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄ (291)	3	74	184	49.48 (49.51)	4.46 (4.35)	24.05 (23.92)
3a	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂ (285)	6	73	225	58.94 (58.85)	5.26 (5.11)	24.56 (24.51)
3b	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₂ Cl (319)	8	77	210	52.66 (52.71)	4.38 (4.41)	21.94 (21.89)
3c	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₄ (330)	11	72	241	50.90 (50.93)	4.24 (4.25)	25.45 (25.34)
4a	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ (300)	10	69	305	60.00 (59.95)	5.30 (5.27)	18.66 (18.67)
4b	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ Cl (334)	8	74	327	53.89 (53.97)	4.49 (4.41)	16.76 (17.70)
4c	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₅ (345)	12	79	347	52.17 (52.11)	4.34 (4.32)	20.28 (20.31)
5a	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ (270)	5	71	214	62.22 (62.12)	5.18 (5.20)	20.74 (20.69)
5b	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ Cl (304)	7	74	202	55.26 (55.34)	4.27 (4.23)	18.42 (18.35)
5c	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄ (315)	8	68	235	53.33 (53.35)	4.12 (4.10)	22.22 (22.19)

and efficient MW assisted procedure for the synthesis of some novel pyrimidinone derivatives of biological significance, which leads to high yields, within very short reaction time and with simplified and safe work up. Further research related to biological assay of synthesized compounds, is underway.

Experimental

Melting points of all the synthesized compounds were determined in open capillary tube and are uncorrected. All reactions were carried out in a commercially available domestic microwave oven (Kenstar Model No. OM 26 EGO) having a maximum power out put of 900 W operating at 2450 MHz. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded using a Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz, FT NMR) with CDCl₃ or DMSO-*d*₆ as solvents using TMS as internal standard. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on FTIR RXI

Perkin-Elmer 1800 spectrometer. Mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol SX-102 (FAB) spectrometer. Spectral data are given in Table 2. The purity of the compounds was checked by elemental analysis and also by TLC using silica gel "G", as absorbent and visualization was accomplished by iodine. Elemental analysis was carried out on Elementar vario EL III carlo Erba 1108. Physical and analytical data of the synthesized compounds are given in Table 1.

Synthesis of 4-aryl-6-methyl-2-pyrimidinone-5-carbohydrazides (2a-c) :

To a mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 mL) was added hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol) followed by the addition of little amount of acetic acid. The reaction mixture was taken in an Erlenmeyer conical flask with loose funnel top and irradiated in an unmodified household

Table 2. Spectral data of the synthesized compounds

Compd.	IR (cm ⁻¹)	¹ H NMR (δ)	MS (<i>m/z</i>)
2a	3350, 3280 (NH str.), 2950, 2865 (CH), 1660 (C=O), 1450, 1375 cm ⁻¹ (CH ₃ bend)	2.01 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.23 (2H, s, NH ₂), 5.23 (1H, s, CH-4), 7.15–8.01 (5H, m, Ar-H), 9.72–10.12 (br.s, NH)	246, 231, 203, 188, 187, 110, 95, 59
2b	3341, 3199 (NH str.), 2962, 2866 (CH), 1680 (C=O), 1445, 1371 (CH ₃ bend), 1037 cm ⁻¹ (Ar-Cl str.)	2.11 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.30 (2H, s, NH ₂), 5.27 (1H, s, CH-4), 7.17–7.68 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.99–8.23 (2H, m, Ar-H), 9.75–10.73 (br.s, NH)	280, 265, 237, 222, 221, 110, 95, 59
2c	3401, 3277 (NH str.), 2971, 2873 (CH), 1674 (C=O), 1447, 1365 (CH ₃ bend), 1555, 1342 cm ⁻¹ (NO ₂ str.)	2.14 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.33 (2H, s, NH ₂), 5.14 (1H, s, CH-4), 7.26–8.17 (4H, m, Ar-H), 9.53–10.42 (br.s, NH)	291, 276, 248, 233, 232, 110, 95, 59
3a	3300 (NH str.), 2926 (CH str.), 1690 (C=O), 1621 cm ⁻¹ (C=N)	2.03 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.69 (2H, s, CH-6 triazinone ring), 5.12 (1H, s, CH-4), 7.11–8.19 (5H, m, Ar-H), 9.75–10.35 (br.s, NH)	285, 187, 165, 144, 110, 98, 95, 77, 70
3b	3411 (NH str.), 2964, 2851 (CH str.), 1685 (C=O), 1624 (C=N), 1043 cm ⁻¹ (Ar-Cl str.)	2.17 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.66 (2H, s, CH-6 triazinone ring), 5.17 (1H, s, CH-4), 7.17–7.81 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.85–8.33 (2H, m, Ar-H), 9.63–10.43 (br.s, NH)	319, 221, 178, 165, 111, 110, 98, 95, 76, 70
3c	3317 (NH str.), 2966 (CH str.), 1693 (C=O), 1631 (C=N), 1551, 1335 cm ⁻¹ (NO ₂ str.)	2.12 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.71 (2H, s, CH-6 triazinone ring), 5.24 (1H, s, CH-4), 7.22–8.21 (4H, m, Ar-H), 9.25–10.15 (br.s, NH)	330, 232, 189, 165, 122, 110, 98, 95, 76, 70
4a	3342 (NH str.), 2960 (CH str.), 1689 cm ⁻¹ (C=O)	2.11 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.73 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 5.4 Hz, CH-5 of pyridazindione ring), 3.31 (1H, t, <i>J</i> 5.4 Hz, CH-4 of pyridazindione ring), 5.12 (1H, s, CH-4), 7.02–7.63 (5H, m, Ar-H), 9.65–10.22 (br.s, NH)	300, 223, 187, 180, 144, 113, 110, 77
4b	3331 (NH str.), 2963 (CH), 1699 cm ⁻¹ (C=O)	2.14 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.79 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 5.3 Hz, CH-5 of pyridazindione ring), 3.37 (1H, t, <i>J</i> 5.3 Hz, CH-4 of pyridazindione ring), 5.39 (1H, s, CH-4), 7.12–7.83 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.85–8.27 (2H, m, Ar-H), 9.35–10.32 (br.s, NH)	334, 223, 221, 180, 178, 113, 111, 110, 76
4c	3410 (NH str.), 2952 (CH str.), 1681 cm ⁻¹ (C=O)	2.17 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.81 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 5.6 Hz, CH-5 of pyridazindione ring), 3.53 (1H, t, <i>J</i> 5.6 Hz, CH-4 of pyridazindione ring), 5.21 (1H, s, CH-4), 7.22–8.23 (4H, m, Ar-H), 9.85–10.92 (br.s, NH)	345, 232, 223, 189, 180, 122, 113, 110, 76
5a	3300 (NH str.) 1690 (C=O), 1611 cm ⁻¹ (C=N)	2.10 (3H, s, CH ₃), 4.14 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2.8 Hz, CH pyrazolinone ring), 5.33 (1H, s, CH-4), 7.03–7.39 (5H, m, Ar-H), 8.33 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2.8 Hz, N=CH pyrazolinone ring), 9.91–10.35 (br.s, NH)	270, 193, 187, 150, 110, 83, 77, 56, 40
5b	3313 (NH str.) 1683 (C=O), 1625 cm ⁻¹ (C=N)	2.13 (3H, s, CH), 4.25 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2.6 Hz, CH pyrazolinone ring), 5.39 (1H, s, CH-4), 7.03–7.24 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.27–7.93 (2H, m, Ar-H), 8.43 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2.6 Hz, N=CH pyrazolinone ring), 9.17–10.15 (br.s, NH)	304, 221, 193, 150, 111, 110, 83, 76, 56, 40
5c	3285 (NH str.), 2954 (CH str.), 1685 (C=O), 1615 cm ⁻¹ (C=N)	2.20 (3H, s, CH ₃), 4.37 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2.9 Hz, CH pyrazolinone ring), 5.41 (1H, s, CH-4), 7.14–8.16 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.39 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2.9 Hz, N=CH pyrazolinone ring), 9.19–10.43 (br.s, NH)	315, 232, 193, 150, 122, 110, 83, 56, 46, 40

microwave oven for 2.5–3 min (at full power of 900 W). After cooling the solvent was removed under reduced pressure, the solid was separated and recrystallized from ethanol.

Synthesis of 3-(6-methyl-2-oxo-4-substituted phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-5-yl)-1,6-dihydro-1,2,4-triazin-5(2H)-one (3a-c) :

To a solution of **2a-c** (0.01 mol) in DMF (20 mL), chloroacetamide (0.01 mol) were added and placed in the microwave oven and irradiated at full power for 6–11 min, then left to cool to room temperature and poured into ice water. The resulting solid was collected by filtration, dried and recrystallized from ethanol.

Synthesis of 4-(6-methyl-2-oxo-4-substituted phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidin-5-yl)tetrahydropyridazine-3,6-dione (4a-c) :

To a solution of **2a-c** (0.01 mol) in DMF (20 mL), chloroacetylchloride was added in a conical flask and placed in the microwave oven and irradiated at full power for 10–12 min. Reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature and poured into ice. The resultant solid was filtered off and washed with cold water. The crude product was purified by recrystallization.

Synthesis of 6-methyl-5-(5-oxo-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-4-substituted phenyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (5a-c) :

Compound **2a-c** (0.01 mol) and triethylorthoformate (20 mL) was heated under microwave irradiation for 5–10 min (at full power of 900 W). The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature; formed solid was separated and filtered off. Further purification was carried out by crystallization.

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